

MODERN INNOVATIVE APPROACH TO PROFESSIONAL TRAINING

Authors: Abdukadirova Xalida Abduxamedovna¹, Mukumova Nargis Nuriddinovna²

Affiliation: associate Professor, Samarkand branch of Tashkent University of Economics ¹, senior lecturer, Samarkand State University of Architecture and Construction²

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the study of innovative methods in the development of human resources in the context of rapid social and economic transformations. It emphasizes that modern organizations increasingly view human capital as their main competitive advantage, which necessitates the introduction of new approaches to personnel training, motivation, and professional growth. The paper analyzes current trends in human resource management, including the integration of digital technologies, e-learning platforms, artificial intelligence, and competency-based approaches in the development of employees. Special attention is given to the formation of innovative corporate culture, continuous learning, and talent management systems aimed at improving organizational performance.

Keywords: innovative economy, personnel innovations, personnel selection, innovations, innovative personnel management structure, innovative personnel training centers.

INTRODUCTION

Modernisation of education and global digitalisation requires the future teacher to be able to use digital or information technologies. Pervasiveness of distance learning and application of artificial intelligence makes it necessary for a modern teacher to develop or acquire information competences

Today, the most successful and sustainable countries are those that implement innovative development models and "smart" technologies. The sustainable progress of such countries, their competitiveness in the world market is based not on the export of natural resources and the use of physical labor, but on innovative ideas and developments.

In these countries, the implementation of the state strategy for the introduction of innovative ideas, developments and technologies is carried out by special departments, conventionally called "ministries of the future".

The main mission of the departments responsible for innovative development is to increase economic growth, the country's competitiveness in world markets and increase the intellectual contribution to the economy through the widespread introduction of innovations and scientific achievements.

MAIN PART

The Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 outlines specific goals for a radical increase in the well-being and improvement of the quality of life of the population, comprehensive and

accelerated development of society and the state, modernization of the country and liberalization of all spheres of life. In other words, we have to turn Uzbekistan into a dynamically developing country with a stable market economy with a high share of innovative and intellectual contribution to production, modern and competitive industry in the global market, as well as a favorable investment and business climate. [1]

Personnel innovations are targeted activities for the implementation of personnel innovations aimed at increasing the level and ability of personnel to solve problems of effective functioning and development of socio-economic structures (organizations and their divisions) in the conditions of competition in the markets of goods, labor and educational (professional and qualification) services. Personnel innovations are one of the types of innovations and are used in the personnel work of enterprises, institutions and organizations. They are the main component of innovative management in personnel work, represent a complex process of creation, dissemination and use of innovations and simply innovations that have practical interest in the work of the organization's personnel services. The search for highly qualified workers is a pressing problem for most modern enterprises in the conditions of the domestic economy.

Competent and high-quality hiring of personnel can repeatedly increase the efficiency of companies, while the personnel selection system should be based on the constant improvement of methods of working with personnel and the use of innovative achievements of foreign and domestic science, as well as the best production experience.

A detailed approach to the process of personnel selection guarantees the quality of labor resources, which largely determines the efficiency and possibility of further use. Quite recently, one of the main indicators of the innovative development of an organization was the number of technical innovations, inventions and the degree of their use, but innovations in management activities were not considered. Although the implementation of the achievements of scientific and technological progress and their dissemination are facilitated by management innovations.

In recent years, a surge in innovative activity can be seen in our country, which can be seen in the diagram:

Diagram 1. Number of innovations implemented

Distinctive features that innovative personnel should have are, first of all, widely developed abilities to provide new ideas, non-standard solutions, creative thinking, knowledge for the implementation of new developments and striving for innovative changes. A special role in the training of innovative personnel is given to higher education institutions. Their main task is to attract students and teachers to research work, to designate the innovative economy as a goal, to provide the necessary resources and tools for the development of fundamental and applied research. Continuous development and focus on results in personnel training will allow universities to maintain their positions in the educational market and meet the requirements of the state's innovation policy.

In Uzbekistan in 2023, 3,571 researchers were approved for scientific degrees. Of these, 3,100 were approved for the scientific degree of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), and 471 were approved for the scientific degree of Doctor of Science (DSc).

During this period, 2,384 applicants were approved for scientific titles, including 455 for professors, 1,749 for associate professors, and 180 for senior research fellows. During the current period, 33 scientific councils were established.

79 diplomas of scientific degrees issued by institutions of foreign countries were nostrified. Of these, 22 are diplomas of Doctor of Science, 57 are diplomas of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD). Nordic recognition of diplomas of Doctor of Philosophy issued in foreign countries as doctors of science in accordance with the established procedure for scientific degrees was organized.

The main increase in the number of candidates of science is observed in economic, legal, pedagogical and psychological sciences. In order to attract young specialists to science, it is necessary to develop a number of mechanisms that will not only provide this area with personnel, but also create conditions for healthy competition.

Such mechanisms include:[2]

- reforming the remuneration system in science and education;
- introducing new forms of financing fundamental and applied science;
- allocating government subsidies, providing grants, loans, developing venture financing.

The key factor in innovative development is human capital.

CONCLUSION

The innovative path of development that Uzbekistan is following leads to the formation of a new social type of people who will determine the development of the country in the future. Education today affects all spheres of human life and helps to form economic, political, moral and highly cultural potential in an individual. The main role in the formation of human potential belongs to the person himself, his qualitative characteristics. Depending on how his mental and physical health develops, what values a person is guided by when making a decision, what is the basis for the formation of his personality, his further transformation and ability to constantly improve and work on himself are formed.

The development of human potential requires the transformation and improvement of the quality of the social environment and living conditions of people. For this purpose, the priority issues are not only education, but also modernization in the field of demographic policy, health care, culture, pensions and other vital areas. Human development is not only learning, but also maintaining positive results over a long period of time.

The Human Development Index determines the level and quality of life (health, education and income of citizens). The country's course towards an innovative economy will inevitably make its own adjustments to the value orientations of society. A realistic assessment of the changes taking place in the future of the Uzbek economy will allow us to direct the education process along the path of innovative development, developing and using all opportunities for the formation and retention of innovative personnel.

The role of innovation today is too high in all areas of the economy. One of the priority areas for development is the national economic security of the country. Participation of Uzbekistan in various international projects will allow demonstrating the level of development of the country's human potential in the foreign market and attracting foreign human resources. Expansion of the market for high-tech products, modernization of various sectors of the economy will provide an opportunity to strengthen positions in the world market. [4]

Innovative transformation of HR management is primarily aimed at implementing a motivation policy focused on expanding effective interaction between personnel and management to achieve common goals. This encourages employees to develop their potential, to work actively, productively and creatively.

The ongoing transformations require timely identification of possible innovative problem situations in combination with HR management problems. Among the problems that arise in this regard, the following contradictions can be highlighted:

- between the scientific and technical level of new production and the existing level of personnel qualifications;
- between the ability of educational institutions to train, retrain and improve qualifications and the required qualifications of personnel;
- between qualitatively new tasks of employee development and insufficient level of preparation of the HR service for this work;
- between the level of motivation and qualifications of employees;
- between elite personnel and the bulk of the company's personnel;
- between the existing organizational structure and the implemented HR strategy, etc.

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